

Colorimetric Determination of Urea in Potable Water using Diacetyldioxime and different Oxidising Agents

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Urea is known to be nauseous and causes loss of sodium and potassium from body when present in potable water¹. Water samples collected from places nearby urea-producing factories are sometimes found to be contaminated with it. A number of methods of its determination are known, such as gasometric method in which nitrogen is produced through its alkali-hypobromite oxidation², ammonia liberation method through its enzymatic hydrolysis by urease³, and colorimetric methods like (i) its chlorination with hypochlorite followed by addition of phenol to produce a canary yellow product⁴, (ii) reaction of urea with *p*-diethylaminobenzaldehyde⁵ or with acetyloxime⁶, (iii) formation of urea-diacetylmonoxime^{7,8} etc.

The purpose of the presentation is to report. (i) a new direct colorimetric method of determination of urea in potable water using diacetyldioxime in presence of oxidising agents like ferric ion (ferric alum), ceric ion (ceric sulphate) or selenic acid, in the presence or absence of a colour intensifier semicarbazide and (ii) a comparative study of the colorimetric results with those obtained by using the conductometric method for the same water samples. An attempt has also been made to determine urea content in some samples of tap-water in Dakhliya province in Egypt and also near the Talkha fertilizer factory there.

Results and Discussions

The results are presented in Table 1. Urea-diacetylmonoxime method is somewhat different

from the method of diacetyldioxime reported therein, although in both these methods magenta colour of the ultimate solution is produced. In the former method, manganous ion and semicarbazide are used, and for the intensification of the colour 10–15% inclusion of potassium persulphate is recommended; however, the presence of the latter compound has been found to cause a gradual fading of the colour even in the absence of light⁹. In the latter method, on the other hand, urea is allowed to react with diacetyldioxime in the presence of oxidising agents to produce yellow colour which on subsequent reaction with semicarbazide produces the magenta colour. The first stage of the reaction has been studied with the oxidising agents like ferric ion (alum), ceric ion (sulphate) and selenic acid. Among these ceric ion has been proved to be most effective since when 4–40, 1–10 and 2–25 μg of urea, each in 25 ml, were treated with Fe^{III} , Ce^{IV} and selenic acid respectively, the solutions absorbed at 475 nm and the observed corresponding molar absorptions were 23 820, 68 950 and 38 210 $\text{dm}^{-3} \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$. Again, a 2 ml solution of urea when treated with 1 ml of Ce^{IV} -sulphate, 10 ml of acid mixture (H_2SO_4 and H_3PO_4), 0.6 ml of diacetyldioxime and 2 ml of semicarbazide, produced a solution with maximum absorbance at 520 nm; and Beer's law has been found to obey in the concentration range 0.5–5 μg of urea in 25 ml with molar absorptivity 98230.5 $\text{dm}^{-3} \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$.

The conductometric method of determination of urea, described in the experimental section, has been found to be equally reliable for a

TABLE 1— DETERMINATION OF UREA COLORIMETRICALLY AND CONDUCTOMETRICALLY

Colorimetrically				Conductometrically	
Ceric-diacetyldioxime		Ceric-diacetyldioxime + semicarbazide		Concn.	Recovery
Concn.	Recovery	Concn.	Recovery	g	%
ppm	%	ppm	%		
0.20	98.80	0.10	98.85	1.2×10^{-1}	98.82
0.25	98.83	0.15	98.87	1.2×10^{-2}	98.84
0.30	98.83	0.20	98.88	1.2×10^{-3}	98.86
0.40	98.85	0.25	98.92	1.2×10^{-4}	98.88
0.45	98.95	0.30	98.95	1.2×10^{-5}	98.95
0.50	99.00	0.35	98.96	1.2×10^{-6}	98.98
Mean	98.88		98.91		98.89
Relative error	0.004		0.005		0.002
t'	1.43				1.54

t' calculated is 2.26 with 10 degrees of freedom.

wide range of concentration (viz. 1.2×10^{-5} to 1.2×10^{-1} g nitrogen in urea). A statistical comparison of the results is shown in Table 1.

Considering the results obtained by the colorimetric method in the presence of semicarbazide as standard, using the student's t test no significant disagreement in the results between the two methods is revealed. The t calculated is less than that tabulated (2.26, probability = 0.05) with 10 degrees of freedom. These methods are applied for the determination of urea in some tap-water samples of Dakhliya province. Out of six samples, collected at random, the urea content in five was under the limit of the present methods of detection and determination. Only one sample nearby the Talkha fertilizer factory, was found to contain ~ 0.5 ppm of urea (average of the results obtained by using the present three methods).

Experimental

The chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The water used for preparative works was made ammonia-free and demineralised. Ferric alum reagent (1%) was prepared by dissolving it in 80 ml acid mixture (85% phosphoric acid and sulphuric acid, 1 : 2, v/v) and then made up to 100 ml with water. Diacetyldioxime (0.6%, w/v) and ceric sulphate (0.5%) were prepared

in 0.1 N sodium hydroxide and 0.1 N sulphuric acid respectively. Solutions of sodium chloride (15%), selenic acid (0.2%, w/v) from crystalline acid, semicarbazide (0.6%, w/v), hydrazinium sulphate (2%), manganous sulphate (2%) and stock solution of urea (1 mg ml⁻¹) were prepared in the above mentioned processed water. Dilute urea solutions (1 and 0.1 μ g ml⁻¹) were prepared by serial dilution of its stock solution with this water.

Spectrophotometric measurements and conductometric measurements were performed by using a Unicam S.P. 1800 spectrophotometer with 1 cm glass cells and a conductometer (Linton, WPA, Cambridge CM 35, equipped with dip cell CM3 having cell constant = 1.024) respectively.

All measurements were carried out at room temperature ($\sim 25^\circ$).

Procedures :

Colorimetric method without semicarbazide :
To the water sample (2 ml) were added diacetyldioxime (0.5 ml), sodium chloride (3 ml), H₂SO₄/H₃PO₄ mixture (10 ml) and any of the oxidising agents (2ml F^{III}-alum, or 1 ml Ce^{IV}-sulphate, or 4.0 ml selenic acid), and the mixture was heated for 10 min in boiling water, then cooled to room temperature and made up to 25 ml with distilled water. Absorbancy of the

NOTE

solution was read at 475 nm against a reagent blank. For urea content in the unknown samples, separate calibration curves were prepared using the above three oxidising agents and 4–40, 1–10 and 2–20 µg of urea in 25 ml respectively.

Colorimetric method with semicarbazide : To the water sample (5 ml), all those steps using Ce^{IV} -sulphate as described above were followed, but before making up the volume to 25 ml with water, the semicarbazide reagent (2 ml) was added and the colour of the solution was measured at 520 nm against a reagent blank. Calibration curves were prepared using 0.5 to 5.0 µg of urea in 25 ml.

Conductometric method : To a mixture of the water sample (known volume), manganous sulphate (5 ml), hydrogen peroxide (0.5 ml) and hydrazinium sulphate (5 ml) diluted to about 100 ml with ammonia and urea-free water, was added 10% NaOH (50 ml) and then distilled carefully for 30–40 min under gentle boiling. The liberated ammonia was received in a known volume of standard HCl (10^{-2} – 10^{-4} M). The excess acid retained was titrated with standard NaOH solution (0.01 M) and the conductivity was measured after each addition of the titrant

(0.05 ml at a time). From a plot of the conductivity vs. volume of titrant, the end-point was determined by the usual method.

References

1. A. C. GUYTON, "Textbook of Medical Physiology", 6th. ed., W. B. Saunders, Philadelphia, 1981.
2. A. I. VOGLI, "Elementary Practical Organic Chemistry", ELBS, London, 1958, Part III, p. 833.
3. W. T. CHIN and W. KROONJE, *Anal. Chim.*, 1961, **33**, 1757; Y. I. TUR'YAN and A. A. KAKOS'YAN, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1982, **97**, 192573; C. VRATISLAV and M. JIRI, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1976, **84**, 212160.
4. G. K. EHRHARDT and K. KRLEHMING, "Method of Sea Water Analysis", 2nd. ed., Verlag-Chemie, Weinheim, 1983, p. 159.
5. G. G. MCCARHY, *Limanol Oceanogr.*, 1970, **15**, 309; H. M. SAYLD, F. B. SALEM and N. A. SALAM, *Int. J. Ecol. Environ. Sci.*, 1991, 17.
6. J. E. MCLESKEY, *Anal. Chem.*, 1964, **33**, 1757
7. B. S. NEWELL, B. MORGAN and J. GUNDY, *J. Marine Res.*, 1967, **25**, 201.
8. K. MATSUNAGA and M. NISHIMURA, *Bunseki Kagaku*, 1972, **21**, 138 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1973, **78**, 128129).
9. R. C. HOSNEY and K. F. FINNLY, *Anal. Chem.*, 1964, **36**, 2145.

